

FACTORS RELATED TO ANXIETY LEVELS IN PREOPERATIVE SECTIO CAESAREA PATIENTS

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Abstract

In Indonesia, 29.0% experience anxiety and fear when going through labor, the fear felt can be in the form of fear that the baby to be born will be deformed, pain during surgery, fear of surgery failure and bleeding during surgery. The purpose of the study was to determine what factors were related to the level of anxiety in pre-operative caesarean section patients at RSIA Restu Bunda, Bandar Lampung City in 2024. The researcher used an analytical survey design with a cross-sectional approach. The study population was all mothers who had pre-operative caesarean sections. Data collection was carried out on February 19-March 19, 2024 at RSIA Restu Bunda, Bandar Lampung City. The population of pre-operative caesarean section patients, the sampling technique used accidental sampling with a total of 40 respondents. The data analysis method was by univariate and bivariate analysis with the chi-square test. The results of the study showed that there was a relationship between age and anxiety levels (0.005), there was a relationship between parity status and anxiety levels (0.011), there was a relationship between family support and anxiety levels (0.008) and there was a relationship between coping mechanisms and anxiety levels (0.005). It is expected that nurses in dealing with anxiety in pre-operative caesarean section patients can provide health education to patients and families about age at risk, parity status, family support and coping mechanisms.

Keywords: Factors, Anxiety, Pre-operative Caesarean Section.

1. INTRODUCTION

Caesarean section also known as sectio caesarea (CS) is a surgical procedure that involves making an incision in the mother's abdomen (laparotomy) and uterus (hysterectomy) to deliver the baby. Cesarean section is usually performed when vaginal delivery is not possible because it is dangerous with various medical problems. Delivery by Sectio Caesarea is needed as an effort to save the mother and fetus, although currently the trend of giving birth by cesarean section is increasing from year to year, however, every mother who will face a surgical delivery always feels anxious when facing a cesarean section (Naibaho, 2021). Worldwide, it is estimated that there are 5-15% of cesarean sections. Cesarean section deliveries have continued to increase over the past few years, this phenomenon is increasing especially in developed countries and is starting to spread to developing countries especially in Asia, the increase in caesarean section deliveries in all countries since 2007 to 2008 is 110,000 per birth throughout Asia (Who, Unicef, Unfpa, 2019). In Indonesia, the prevalence of cesarean section in childbirth is 17.6%, the highest in DKI Jakarta (31.3%) and the lowest in Papua (6.7%) (Risksdas, 2018) and data for the Lampung province recorded by the Lampung provincial health office in 2018, the number of cesarean section deliveries in Lampung reached 13.2% of mothers aged 10 to 54 years (Lampung Province Profile, 2022). Data from the Indonesian health demographic survey shows that the maternal mortality rate in Indonesia is still quite high. In Indonesia, the infant mortality rate decreased from 32 per 1,000 live births in 2016 to 27 per 1,000 in 2020 (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2020). The success rate of maternal and infant delivery has decreased so that the proportion of the incidence of cesarean section deliveries in Indonesia continues to increase both in government and private hospitals (Alwi et al, 2022).

Anxiety can occur at any age, more often in adulthood and more in women. Most anxiety occurs at the age of 21-45 years. Age can affect anxiety in mothers who are going to give birth that ages under 20 years and 30 years will have an impact on feelings of anxiety the younger the age or the older the risk of the labor process (Naibaho, 2021). Age over 30 years is considered a phase to stop pregnancy, because age over 30 years is an age prone to pregnancy and is included in the high-risk pregnancy category. This is because the level of risk of morbidity and mortality in the mother and fetus will increase compared to pregnancy at the age of 20-30 years (Hanifah, 2019). The most common response in preoperative patients is anxiety. This anxiety arises because patients have perceptions of surgical procedures such as death, disability, pain during or after surgery and failure of private surgery (Alwi et al, 2022). In March-April 2020, the number of deliveries by Caesarean section at RSIA Restu Bunda reached 83 people (Widiyawati, 2021). In 2022, an average of 50 patients underwent Caesarean section surgery at RSIA Restu Bunda per month (Rizky, 2023). Surgery is a potential or actual threat to a person's integrity and can subsequently cause physiological and psychological stress reactions (Naibaho, 2021). Anxiety is a clinical symptom experienced by individuals receiving medical care, the healing process will be hampered if anxiety in preoperative patients is not treated immediately. Before surgical intervention is carried out, patients receive initial preparation, during this stage patients and medical personnel carry out various preparatory actions to ensure that there are no obstacles during surgery or recovery, patients who will undergo surgery are likely to experience anxiety, anxiety is characterized by worry, fear and feelings of helplessness (Fatrida & Tanjung, 2023). Anxiety disorders and depressive disorders are the most common types of mental disorders. An estimated 4.4% of the world's population has a depressive disorder and 3.6% have anxiety conditions. Asia Pacific region in 2012, India had 56,675,969 cases, or 4.5% of the population, of depression and anxiety disorders, while the Maldives had 12,739 cases, or 3.7% of the population. Meanwhile, 3.7% of the population or 9,162,886 cases were reported in Indonesia (WHO 2017 in Riskesdas, 2018). In Indonesia, 29.0% experienced anxiety and fear when going to give birth, the fear felt can be in the form of fear that the baby to be born will be deformed, pain during surgery, fear of surgery failure and bleeding during surgery (Widyastuti, 2021).

Everyone who is going to undergo surgery has different levels of anxiety, some experience mild, moderate, severe anxiety or even panic. In pre-operative patients who experience high levels of anxiety or fear, it is a maladaptive reaction that can interfere with physiological processes such as frequent urination or diarrhea, narrowed field of vision, headaches and difficulty concentrating. In addition, several things that also affect the level of anxiety in the process leading up to surgery, including age, level of knowledge, family support, experience, coping mechanisms, and parity status (in mothers giving birth), several of these factors can hinder the surgical process, until the patient's vital signs are in a safe range for action, if the patient experiences increasing physiological problems (Suhadi, Pratiwi, 2020). In a study entitled The relationship between maternal age and anxiety levels in patients undergoing first-time cesarean section surgery, it was concluded that the results of the study showed that there was a relationship between maternal age and anxiety levels in patients undergoing first-time cesarean section surgery, showing a figure of 0.049 ($p < 0.05$) (Alwi, et al (2022). Another study entitled parity status with anxiety levels in mothers pre-cesarean section surgery and concluded that there was a significant relationship between parity status and anxiety in mothers pre-cesarean section surgery. Most mothers who feel anxious are due to having no previous experience, namely childbirth by cesarean section (Susanti, Utama (2022). And based on a study entitled Factors that influence anxiety levels in pre-operative patients, it was concluded that there was an influence of personality type ($p = 0.027$), coping mechanisms ($p = 0.005$) and family support ($p = 0.016$) on the level of anxiety in pre-operative patients (Hartono, Dayat (2020).

This study aims to determine the factors that related to the level of anxiety in pre-operative caesarean section patients at RSIA Restu Bunda, Bandar Lampung City in 2024. The hypothesis in this study is that there is a relationship between age, parity status, family support and coping mechanisms with the level of anxiety in pre-operative caesarean section patients at RSIA Restu Bunda, Bandar Lampung City in 2024.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study is a quantitative research type, analytical research design with a cross-sectional approach. This study was conducted in the VK room and maternity care at RSIA Restu Bunda, Bandar Lampung City in 2024. This study was conducted on February 19 - March 19, 2024. The population in this study were pre-operative caesarean section patients with an average number of patients per month of 50 at RSIA Restu Bunda, Bandar Lampung City. This study used a random sampling technique with accidental sampling. The sample in this study was 40 pre-operative caesarean section patients in the VK room and maternity care at RSIA Restu Bunda, Bandar Lampung City. Inclusion criteria: 1) patients who will give birth by caesarean section 2) Patient aged 17 to 50 years 3) Patient with a delivery status or parity status < 4 time. Exclusion criteria: Patients who will have a normal delivery or vaginal birth. The independent variables are age, parity status, family support and coping mechanisms while the dependent variable is the level of anxiety in pre-operative caesarean section patients. The data collection instrument in this study used an age and parity status observation sheet and a family support, coping mechanism and anxiety questionnaire sheet. Data analysis was carried out using the chi-square test, and this research has received ethical clearance from the Tanjungkarang Health Polytechnic, with the ethical clearance number: No.134/KEPK-TJK/II/2024.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Characteristics of Research Respondents

Table 1. Distribution of Frequency Characteristics of Respondents at RSIA Blessing Bunda Bandar Lampung City in 2024

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
Not at Risk	24	60
At Risk	16	40
Total	40	100
Parity Status		
Primigravida	16	40
Multigravida	24	60
Total	40	100
Family Support		
Positive Support	31	77.5
Negative Support	9	22.5
Total	40	100
Coping Mechanism		
Adaptive	32	80
Maladaptive	8	20
Total	40	100

Based on the results of the study in table 1, it can be seen that the age of the respondents is mostly at risk, namely 24 people (60%), the most parity status is multigravida, namely 24 people (60%), the most family support is positive support, namely 31 people (77.5%) and the most coping mechanism is adaptive, namely 32 people (80%).

Table 2. Frequency Distribution Analysis of Anxiety Levels in Pre-Caesarean Section Patients at RSIA Restu Bunda, Bandar Lampung City in 2024

Anxiety Level	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Mild Anxiety	6	15
Moderate Anxiety	20	50
Severe Anxiety	14	35
Total	40	100

Based on the results of the study in table 4.2, it was obtained from 40 respondents that the results of the study were dominated by pre-operative caesarean section patients who experienced anxiety. As many as 6 respondents (15%) experienced mild anxiety, There were 20 respondents (50%) experiencing moderate anxiety and as many as 14 respondents (35%) experiencing severe anxiety.

There are several factors that can influence anxiety in pre-operative caesarean section patients, according to Stuart (2013) are Age, Parity Status, Family Support, Coping Mechanisms, Knowledge and Experience. According to researchers, almost most of the results of the study found that pre-operative caesarean section patients experienced moderate anxiety, the emergence of fear when surgery was to be performed due to several factors, namely age at risk, still very young <20 years and age > 36 years, previous labor status or labor experience is one of the factors causing anxiety due to feeling afraid of surgery, especially in patients who are undergoing caesarean section for the first time, patients who get support from their husbands and families will feel calmer compared to patients who do not get support from their families can cause anxiety due to the burden felt by the patient and patients who feel anxious due to stress will instinctively try to overcome it with various coping techniques.

3.2 Relationship between Age and anxiety levels in pre-operative caesarean section patients

Table 3. Relationship between Age and anxiety levels in pre-operative caesarean section patients

Age	Anxiety						Total n	p-value	OR (95% CI)
	Mild		Moderate		Severe				
	n	%	n	%	n	%			
Not at Risk	2	8.3	17	12	5	20.8	24	0.005	4.005 (0.307–52.260)
At Risk	4	25	3	18.8	9	56.2	16		
Total	6	15	20	50	14	35	40		

Based on the results of the study, it was obtained from 24 respondents with non-risk age (20-35 years) as many as 2 (8.3%) respondents with mild anxiety, as many as 17 respondents (70.8%) experienced moderate anxiety and 5 (20.8%) respondents experienced severe anxiety. The results obtained from 16 respondents with risk age (<20 and > 36 years), as many as 4 (25%) respondents experienced mild anxiety, as many as 3 respondents (18.8%) experienced moderate anxiety and 9 (56.2%) respondents with severe anxiety. The results of the non-parametric test using the chi-square test obtained a p-value = (0.005) < α (0.05) so it was concluded that there was a relationship between age and anxiety levels in pre-operative caesarean section patients at RSIA Restu Bunda, Bandar Lampung City in 2024. The results of the analysis obtained an OR value of 4.005. This is in accordance with Stuart's theory, that one of the internal factors that causes anxiety is age. The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by Naibaho (2021) on "Factors that influence maternal anxiety before cesarean section (SC) surgery at Sidikalang Hospital, Dairi Regency from 55 respondents. The p-value of age was 0.003 ($p < 0.05$) and it was concluded that there was a relationship between maternal age and anxiety levels in patients who would undergo cesarean section surgery.

The results of the study showed that the characteristics of the pre-operative patient age were non-risk age 20-35 years as many as 24 (62.5%) respondents and risk age <20 years and > 36 years as many as 16 (37.5%) respondents. Researchers argue that age is included in the internal factors that influence anxiety and pregnancy. Someone who is younger will be more susceptible

to anxiety disorders than someone who is older, as well as pregnancy at an age that is too young and too old is included in the criteria for high-risk pregnancy where both play a role in increasing morbidity and mortality in the mother and fetus.

3.3 Relationship between Parity Status and anxiety levels in pre-operative patients with Sectio Caesarea

Table 4. Relationship between Parity Status and anxiety levels in pre-operative patients with Sectio Caesarea

Parity Status	Anxiety						Total n	p-value	OR (95% CI)
	Mild		Moderate		Severe				
	n	%	n	%	n	%			
Primigravida	1	6.2	5	31.2	10	62.5	16	0.011	0.125 (0.011–1.360)
Multigravida	5	20.8	15	62.5	4	16.7	24		
Total	6	15	20	50	14	35	40		

Based on the results of the study, the values obtained from 16 respondents with primigravida parity status (first time delivery), as many as 1 (6.2%) respondents experienced mild anxiety, as many as 5 respondents (31.2%) experienced moderate anxiety and 10 (62.5%) respondents with severe anxiety. The results obtained from 24 respondents with multigravida parity status (delivery > 1 time), as many as 5 (20.8%) respondents experienced mild anxiety, as many as 15 (62.5%) respondents experienced moderate anxiety and 4 (16.7%) respondents experienced severe anxiety. The p-value = (0.011) < α (0.05) then it is concluded that there is a relationship between parity status and anxiety levels in pre-operative caesarean section patients at RSIA Restu Bunda, Bandar Lampung City in 2024. The results of the analysis obtained an OR value of 0.125 and a 95% CI interval of 0.011-1.360, which means that patients with primigravida parity status have a 0.125 times greater chance of experiencing mild, moderate and severe anxiety compared to patients with multigravida parity status.

The condition of a woman called parity is related to how many children she has given birth to. When mothers experience primiparous pregnancy for the first time, they become increasingly nervous as they approach the third trimester of their pregnancy because they are getting closer to delivery. Anxiety related to pregnancy and fear of childbirth are common for mothers. Mothers who have given birth before are called multigravida, it could be that the fear comes from their previous experiences (Taufik, 2022). Based on the results of the study, the characteristics of the parity status of pre-operative caesarean section patients were Primigravida (first time delivery) as many as 18 (62.5%) respondents and Multigravida (delivery >1 time). The researcher argues that patients who will undergo their first delivery by caesarean section will be more likely to experience anxiety compared to patients who have had more than one delivery experience.

3.4 Relationship between Family Support and anxiety levels in pre-operative caesarean section patients

Table 5. Relationship between Family Support and anxiety levels in pre-operative caesarean section patients

Family Support	Anxiety						Total n	p-value	OR (95% CI)
	Mild		Moderate		Severe				
	n	%	n	%	n	%			
Positive	5	16.1	19	61.3	7	22.6	31	0.008	6.245 (0.42–92.816)
Negative	1	11.1	1	11.1	7	77.8	9		
Total	6	15	20	50	14	35	40		

Based on the results of the study, it was found that 31 respondents received family support, 5 (16.1%) respondents experienced mild anxiety, 19 (61.3%) respondents experienced moderate anxiety and 7 (22.6%) respondents experienced severe anxiety. The results obtained from 9 respondents did not receive family support, 1 (11.1%) respondents experienced mild anxiety, 1 (11.1%) respondents experienced moderate anxiety and 7 (77.8%) respondents experienced severe anxiety. The p-value (0.008) $< \alpha$ (0.05) then it is concluded that there is a relationship between family support and anxiety levels in pre-operative caesarean section patients at RSIA Restu Bunda, Bandar Lampung City in 2024. The results of the analysis obtained an OR value of 6,245 and a 95% CI interval of 0.420-92,816 which means that patients with less family support will have a chance of experiencing mild, moderate, severe anxiety of 6,245 times compared to patients who have good family support.

This study is in line with Simanullang's theory, (2020) that the causes of anxiety in pregnant women include lack of family support, financial adequacy, ability to control pregnancy and information about the terrible birth experience, with family support can be about, motivated and relieve stress. There are four types of family support, emotional support, instrumental support, information support and appreciation support.

Based on the results of the study, the characteristics of family support for pre-operative caesarean section patients were Positive (there is support) as many as 23 (62.5%) respondents and Negative (no support) as many as 17 (37.5%) respondents. Researchers argue that the presence and involvement of the family greatly supports the mental preparation of pre-operative patients

3.5 Relationship between Coping Mechanisms and anxiety levels in pre-operative caesarean section patients

Table 6. Relationship between Coping Mechanisms and anxiety levels in pre-operative caesarean section patients

Coping Mechanism	Anxiety						Total	P-value	OR (95% CI)
	Mild		Moderate		Severe				
	n	%	n	%	n	%			
Adaptive	3	9.4	20	62.5	9	28.1	32	0.005	0.257 (0.146–0.452)
Maladaptive	3	37.5	0	0	5	62.5	8		
Total	6	15	20	50	14	35	40		

Based on the results of the study, the values of 32 respondents who experienced adaptive coping mechanisms were 3 (9.4%) respondents experiencing mild anxiety, 20 (62.5%) respondents experiencing moderate anxiety and 9 (28.1%) respondents experiencing severe anxiety. The results were obtained from 8 respondents with maladaptive coping mechanisms, 3 (37.5%) respondents experiencing mild anxiety and 5 (62.5%) respondents experiencing severe anxiety. The P-value = (0.005) $< \alpha$ (0.05) so it is concluded that there is a relationship between coping mechanisms and anxiety levels in pre-operative caesarean section patients at RSIA Restu Bunda, Bandar Lampung City in 2024. The results of the analysis obtained an OR value of 0.257 and a 95% CI interval of 0.146-0.452, which means that patients with maladaptive coping mechanisms will have a chance of experiencing mild, moderate and severe anxiety by 0.257 times compared to adaptive coping mechanisms. This study is in line with Sutejo's theory (2022) Coping techniques will be successful if the person using them feels that the technique can help them get through the situation. To form an individual's physical and psychological balance, anxiety disorders must be treated immediately. Two types of coping strategies are used in anxiety disorders, namely problem-solving strategies and self-defense mechanisms.

Based on the results of the study, 32 respondents had adaptive coping mechanisms and 8 respondents had maladaptive coping mechanisms. The researcher argues that coping mechanisms greatly influence the anxiety that occurs in mothers who will undergo a cesarean section.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that: the a relationship with anxiety levels is age, parity status, family support, coping mechanisms. It is recommended that pregnant women prepare for childbirth with the assistance of Health cadres. The results of this research can be continued for community service activities, so that they are more useful.

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